

POLICY BRIEF

DECODING UNPREDICTABILITY: THE DEBATE ON PREDICTABILITY FOR POLICY CONSIDERATIONS ON LETHAL AUTONOMOUS WEAPONS SYSTEMS

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POLICY STATEMENT

The term "unpredictability" has become a contentious issue among the delegations of the High Contracting Parties at the Group of Governmental Experts of the Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons (CCW/GGE) for Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems (LAWS). It has emerged as a significant point of divergence, not only due to its fundamental importance in the LAWS debate but also because of the lack of a universally accepted definition for the term. The terms "predictability", "unpredictability" or "predictable" are included in four out of the six working papers leading to the session in May 2023 (1, 2, 3, 4).

In light of this, the present Policy Brief aims to capture the ongoing debate surrounding the policy considerations of predictability in Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems (LAWS). It conducts an analysis of a side event that was held during the May 2023 session of the CCW/GGE, focusing on the discussions and perspectives shared during the event. By examining this side event and its insights, I seek to contextualise the different approaches to the topic.

BACKGROUND

The CCW/GGE has been, for the last decade, the main forum for the negotiations on an international treaty for Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems. Currently being only regulated by International Humanitarian Law (IHL) and national or regional legal instruments. The CCW seemed to be the appropriate forum given the wide array of States that it encompasses, including eight out of the nine States with nuclear weapons, with the exception of North Korea (5). We face an important moment in these discussions: we are not witnessing progress at the negotiations at the same rate that we witness progress in AI.

In the context of the 2023 mandate, one of the compromises that have gained the most traction among delegations was the Two-Tier Approach, which consisted in imposing both prohibition and regulations for LAWS. In this context, the debate on predictability would be applicable only in systems that have not been previously discarded in the 'prohibition' section of the regulations (6). Even though in the advanced version of the document produced by the mandate the string "predict" is nowhere to be found (7), in the discussions, the theme of predictable AI/unpredictability in LAWS was present (8),

but given the main argument against it, the lack of a consensual definition of predictability, we can assume that the tradeoff made by the Chair took this into account. Thus, the absence of a clear legal and/or consensual definition for unpredictability poses significant challenges for countries seeking to incorporate this term into discussions. Without a shared framework for interpreting unpredictability, countries may struggle to address its implications and formulate appropriate policies. In an effort to elaborate on this issue, on May 17 2023, a side event took place at the Room XXVII in the Building E of the Palais des Nations. The side event was co-sponsored by the High Contracting Parties (HPC) of Austria, Ireland, Mexico, New Zealand and Switzerland, alongside the HPC, the event was also organized by the Women's International League for Peace and Freedom (WILPF). It consisted of a panel discussion on "Unpredictability in Autonomous Weapons Technology". The panelists were: Taniel Yusef, member of the Advisory Board of the Women's International League for Peace and Freedom (WILPF); Giacomo Persi Paoli, Head of the Security and Technology Programme at UNIDIR; Aidan Liddle, UK Ambassador and Permanent Representative to the Conference on Disarmament in Geneva; and Georgia Hinds, Legal Adviser for new technologies of warfare, Arms and Conduct of Hostilities Unit, ICRC.

FINDINGS

A panelist stated that different disciplines will define them differently, and that in the case of LAWS, different factors contribute to unpredictability, one of which being algorithms. It was stated that we cannot predict the actual step-by-step plan of how the AI system will do that, because AI has a desired output, but the strategy to do that is not fixed, that is, we are not able to predict the specific actions that a system will use to reach its goal, even if we know the set of goals the system has. In this context, the goals setted cannot guarantee appropriate means. The panelist described a trade-off that models make between bias and variance, in order to be able to handle different data, the model must further simplify the way it interprets its data. To clarify this idea, the panelist defined bias as the ability of a model to make assumptions about the data in order to make predictions on new or unseen data. It represents the difference between the predicted values generated by the model and the actual values of the target variable; while variance refers to the extent to which changes in data can affect the outcome of a model. A higher variance indicates that the model is more responsive to changes in the data, while a lower variance suggests that the model is more stable and less influenced by such changes. The test data and simulations can lead to very unpredictable outcomes upon deployment given the difficulty to identify possible bias and the possibility of label leakage (9). Therefore, the panelist concluded that in order to know the actual result of models we must run them all the way, specially because of biases that can produce different results when running the same algorithm on different data.

Highlighting the useful distinction between the concepts of predictability and trust, it was said that at the deployment point of an autonomous system, there is an element of trust of the human

decision-maker in the system deployed. In the unpredictability debate, the trust that humans have in these systems plays a pivotal role. A panelist framed predictability as being based in three dimensions: past performance; the degree in which we can anticipate future performances; and how can we predict the future effects that the system will have? And the elements of predictability as: their technical characteristics (modeling, design); the context in which these systems are deployed (permissive, adversarial, hostile environment); and in the human ability to understand how the system will be operated. It was pointed out that this is where trust comes in. And that sometimes, not trusting the system is the better outcome. In this context, it brought forward the idea of calibrating the trust: knowing when we should trust the systems to behave a certain way. To ensure this, there must be implemented bi-directional trust mechanisms, it is important for these systems not to blindly follow their orders. The concept of intelligent disobedience was articulated for this end, a mechanism to ensure that such systems halt its activities when an order that steps outside of its safety limitations, explained as a metaphor as a guide dog that makes sure that a blind person stops when trying to cross the street.

A panelist framed the question by reminding that any military technology is a tool, not actors with agencies for their own rights, just means for an end that commanders have at their disposal. The commander has to believe that this tool will be able to deliver the objective he orders it to deliver. In this sense, it was highlighted that the level of predictability is context specific, the technology itself and in the parameters that technology is being used. It was stated that it was crucial that commanders have the accountability for choices made in the tools they choose to use and for the results that are achieved by those tools. A panelist considered that no tool will be completely predictable, and posed the question: what level of unpredictability do you tolerate? what sort of systems do you build to make sure that even if that something happens that you don't expect, that the outcome still in the outcome is still within the realm of the acceptable, in the opinion of the panelist, the commander has the need to be sure that it will deliver the military objective, concluding that if that tool is perceived as unpredictable, if you don't trust it, you are not going to use it. Therefore, you wouldn't need to be able to predict exactly how it is going to be the objective, but predictability was defined as having, in the military perspective, the necessary conditions of an expectation to do more or less what you expect and confidence that it will achieve the objectives that you want, being a sufficient condition for this the confidence it as an appropriate tool ensure sufficient conditions for commandant trust. The end of these legal aspects and the training aspects results in making sure that weapons systems are understood, that is that you understand what the parameters are; and you understand how their performance varies in different conditions. It was concluded that only with these conditions commanders are able to make informed choices about the tools that they use and know that the choices that they make are going to achieve the objective. Also, making sure that the people who are deploying, are accountable for the choice they make and are properly trained on the capabilities of the system and what sort of margin of error is tolerable

Another panelist defined predictability as the ability to say or estimate that a specified thing will happen in the future or will be a consequence of something. Focus on the effects, not only what we want the system to do, but also errors and malfunctions. It was added that we need to consider that

when these models are operating in adversarial environments, we are also looking at responses to deceptive or countermeasures. The panelist defined predictability in both a narrow and a broad sense. On one hand, we have technical predictability (narrow) linked to the design and in the understatement of the process through with the system functions. On the other hand, operational predictability (broad), that must take the environment into consideration, is affected by the complexity of the deployment. The panelist stated that both aspects of predictability pose problems with compliance with IHL. In the broader sense, IHL requires weapon users to be able to foresee if weapon users are able to reliably foresee if the usage of such weapon contradicts IHL (anticipation). The panelist also added that specifically regarding the rules of conduct of hostilities, two prohibitions that are linked to the technical predictability, those are: rules prohibiting indiscriminate weapons or indiscriminate attacks. Indiscriminate weapons are those that can't be directed at a specific military objective; and the effects of which can't be limited (ability to control effects), thus creating an implicit requirement: you can predict how it will behave and what the effects will be.

CONCLUSIONS

Even though all panelists agree on the importance of predictability on LAWS, the perspective they approached the theme from had a big impact on what predictability actually entailed. Therefore, we can infer from this scenario that there is not only a divergence in the definition of predictability, but more importantly, there are different ways in which the concept of predictability can be analyzed. but there is an underlying commonality among the multiple definitions, that is: at least in the context of LAWS, predictability is composed of multiple elements. No definition of predictability given on the panel was able to conceive the term without relating at least two elements: the analyzed or factual and the expected or programmed outcome. And usually, only a definition seems insufficient in conveying the idea behind, as we saw a number of participants laying the different components of predictability. Even at the operational level, making predictions about Machine Learning models poses a more complex challenge: when seeking to make predictive inference on AI models, the source code or model structure can be an insufficient condition to do so (10). Common ground was also found in the context specificity of predictability, where adversarial techniques and a hostile environment where, when referred, understood as a source of unpredictability, recalling the trade-off between bias and variance.

“Complex AI agents often exhibit inherent unpredictability: they demonstrate emergent behaviors that are impossible to predict with precision—even by their own programmers.”

– Rahwan, I. & Cebrian, M. (11)

Predictability is not only about an actual execution by the AI model that is coherent with the intended purpose for which it has been deployed, but it encompasses a wider array of challenges than what meets the eye. While operational predictability is deemed inherent to AI systems (12), the debate

helps us understand other restrictions/prohibitions that have synergy with unpredictability, such as: parsing and refusal to comply with inadequate prompting; restrictions on the data sets that are used in training; the necessity of a prohibition for indiscriminate weapons and indiscriminate attacks; and the necessity of proper accountability for the Stakeholders that, by utilising such systems are placing their confidence in such tools.

REFERENCES

- (1) Delegations of Argentina, Ecuador, El Salvador, Colombia, Costa Rica, Guatemala, Kazakhstan, Nigeria, Palestine, Panama, Peru, Philippines, Sierra Leone and Uruguay to the CCW/GGE (2023). *Draft Protocol on Autonomous Weapon Systems (Protocol VI)*. Available at: [https://docs-library.unoda.org/Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons -Group of Governmental Experts on Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems \(2023\)/CCW GGE1 2023 WP.6 2.pdf](https://docs-library.unoda.org/Convention%20on%20Certain%20Conventional%20Weapons%20-%20Group%20of%20Governmental%20Experts%20on%20Lethal%20Autonomous%20Weapons%20Systems%20(2023)/CCW%20GGE1%202023%20WP.6%202.pdf)
- (2) Delegation of Pakistan to the CCW/GGE (2023). *Working Paper - Pakistan*. Available at: [https://docs-library.unoda.org/Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons -Group of Governmental Experts on Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems \(2023\)/CCW GGE1 2023 WP.3 REv.1 0.pdf](https://docs-library.unoda.org/Convention%20on%20Certain%20Conventional%20Weapons%20-%20Group%20of%20Governmental%20Experts%20on%20Lethal%20Autonomous%20Weapons%20Systems%20(2023)/CCW%20GGE1%202023%20WP.3%20REv.1%200.pdf)
- (3) Delegation of the State of Palestine to the CCW/GGE (2023). *Working Paper - State of Palestine*. Available at: [https://docs-library.unoda.org/Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons -Group of Governmental Experts on Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems \(2023\)/CCW GGE1 2023 WP.2 Rev.1.pdf](https://docs-library.unoda.org/Convention%20on%20Certain%20Conventional%20Weapons%20-%20Group%20of%20Governmental%20Experts%20on%20Lethal%20Autonomous%20Weapons%20Systems%20(2023)/CCW%20GGE1%202023%20WP.2%20Rev.1.pdf)
- (4) Delegation of Austria to the CCW/GGE (2023). *Working Paper - Austria*. Available at: [https://docs-library.unoda.org/Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons -Group of Governmental Experts on Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems \(2023\)/CCW GGE1 2023 WP.1 Rev.1.pdf](https://docs-library.unoda.org/Convention%20on%20Certain%20Conventional%20Weapons%20-%20Group%20of%20Governmental%20Experts%20on%20Lethal%20Autonomous%20Weapons%20Systems%20(2023)/CCW%20GGE1%202023%20WP.1%20Rev.1.pdf)
- (5) UNODA (n.d.), High Contracting Parties and Signatories CCW. Available at: <https://disarmament.unoda.org/the-convention-on-certain-conventional-weapons/high-contracting-parties-and-signatories-ccw/>
- (6) Anand, A. & Puscas, I. (2023) *Proposals Related to Emerging Technologies in the Area of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems: A Resource Paper (updated)*. Available at: <https://unidir.org/publication/proposals-related-emerging-technologies-area-lethal-autonomous-weapons-systems-resource>
- (7) UNODA (2023), *Report of the 2023 session of the Group of Governmental Experts on Emerging Technologies in the Area of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems*. Available at:

[https://docs-library.unoda.org/Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons -Group of Governmental Experts on Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems \(2023\)/CCW GGE1 2023 2_Advance_version.pdf](https://docs-library.unoda.org/Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons -Group of Governmental Experts on Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems (2023)/CCW GGE1 2023 2_Advance_version.pdf)

- (8) Varella, L. (2023), *CCW Report*, Vol. 11, No. 3. Available at: <https://reachingcriticalwill.org/images/documents/Disarmament-fora/ccw/2023/gge/reports/CCWR11.3.pdf>
- (9) GOOGLE (n.d.) Label Leakage in *Machine Learning Glossary*. Available at: <https://developers.google.com/machine-learning/glossary?hl=de#label-leakage>
- (10) Rahwan, I., Cebrian, M., Obradovich, N., Bongard, J., Bonnefon, J.-F., Breazeal, C., Crandall, J. W., Christakis, N. A, Couzin, I. D., Jackson, M. O. and Jennings, N. R. (2019) Machine behaviour, *Nature* 568(7753), 477486. DOI: 10.1038/s41586-019-1138-y
- (11) Rahwan, I. & Cebrian, M. (2018) Machine Behavior Needs to be an Academic Discipline. Available at: <https://nautil.us/machine-behavior-needs-to-be-an-academic-discipline-237022/>
- (12) Michel, A. H. (2020). *The Black Box, Unlocked: Predictability and Understandability in Military AI*. Geneva, Switzerland: United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research. doi: 10.37559/SecTec/20/AI1

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